

**AWARENESS AMONG POST GRADUATE STUDENTS ON
DIGITAL INDIA PROGRAMME –A STUDY**

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Introduction:

India is a developing country and it's economy is growing. In all sector use of Information Communication Technology is increased. So why should not it is used for day to day transaction. So any time the different transactions can be done easily and without paperwork, time involved in this transaction can be saved and effectively the work will be completed. Hence Government of India started the Digital India Campaign. Through this campaign the Indian citizens are equipped with different government services. As per Wikipedia.org (2017) this campaign was launched on 1st July 2015 by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, for connecting rural areas with high speed internet network. Along with-it different apps are introduced by the government for the extending it's services to Indian citizen.

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Therefore, every citizen must be aware these facility so they can able to use it effectively for their day today transactions. Hence researches undertaken to study the awareness among Post Graduate students on Digital India Programme.

According to cambrige Dictionary (2017) Awareness menace knowledge that something exists or understanding of a situation at the present time based on information or experience. Therefore for the present research awareness means knowledge or understanding of Digital India Programme among post graduate students of Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

Therefore present research is undertaken with three objectives these are-

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To Study the components of Digital India Programme.
- 2) To Study the awareness among Post Graduate students on Digital India Programme.
- 3) To make appropriate suggestions on the basis of the study.

Research Method and Procedure

For present research survey method is adopted to study post graduate students' awareness on digital India programme.

Sample of the Study

For the Selection of the Sample incidental sampling technique is used from sample selection method Non-Probability.

Collection of the Data

Questionnaire was prepared by the researcher which consists of 25 questions with four choices. The questionnaire consists of eight dimensions name Digital India Programme, Digi Locker, SBM, e-Sign, e-Hospital, National Scholarship, e- Attendance, User of Digital India app.

Statistical technique

Percentage statistical technique is used for analyzing the collected data.

Objective wise procedure of the study

For the smooth functioning of the research objective wise procedure is followed. It is discussed as follows.

The first objective of the study is to Study the components of Digital India Programme. Therefore for fulfillment of this objectives review of literature is undertaken i.e.

After reviewing digitalindia.gov.in (2017), Wikipedia (2017) quora.com (2017), vikaspedia (2017) these component are identified Digital India Programme, Digi Locker, Swachha Bharat Mission(SBM), e-sign, e-Hospital, National Scholarship, e-attendance etc.

Figure No.1
Component of Digital India Programme

Digital India Programme	Digital India aims to provide the much needed thrust to the nine pillars of growth areas, namely Broadband highways, Universal Access to Mobile Connectively, Public Internet Access Programme, e- Governance- Reforming government through Technology, e- Kranti- Electronic Delivery of Service, Information for All, Electronic Manufacturing, IT of job and Early Harvest programme. Each of these areas is a complex programme in itself and across multiple Ministries and Departments.
Digi Locker	DigiLocker is a platform for issuance and verification of documents & certificates in a digital way, thus eliminating the use of physical documents
SBM	The <i>Swachh Bharat</i> mission's app would be used by people and Government organizations.
e-Sign	An initiative to eradicate forgery and fraudulent signature, the eSign framework would allow citizens to digitally sign a document online using Aadhaar authentication.
e-Hospital	This initiative aims at providing timely, effective and economical health care services to all, especially to the ones that have little access to healthcare services. This service too will be linked to Aadhaar numbers, and will make getting lab reports and OPD appointments easier. The Online Registration System (ORS) under the e-Hospital application has also been introduced.
National Scholarship Portal	This new service is said to be a one-stop-solution for end-to-end scholarship process right from submission of student application, verification, sanction and disbursal to end beneficiary for all the scholarships provided by the Government of India.

e- attendance	A web based application software system will enable online recording of attendance and its viewing by the concerned stakeholders.
Users of Digital India apps	The Indian government has launched a number of mobile applications for all major Smartphone platforms. These apps range from education, agriculture, healthcare to e Governance. We have prepared a list of key application that comply with Digital India initiative as well as make our lives easier.

The Second objective of the study is to study the awareness among Post Graduate students on Digital India Programme. For fulfillment this objective researchers has made 25 questions multiple choice questionnaire, data is collected from these post graduate students from the departments of shivaji university and result of it are shown in Figure No. 2

From figure no. 2 it seems that post graduate male students have more awareness on Digital India Programme, Digi locker and Digital India app comparatively to female students. However post graduate female students have more awareness on SBM, e-Sign, e-Hospital, national Scholarship etc Comparatively to male students. However post graduate female and male students have similar awareness on e- attendance.

DISCUSSION

Post Graduate students have very less awareness on national scholarship, e- Hospital, Digi Locker etc.

Thus, the second objective of the study is fulfilled and the third of objective of the study is to make appropriate suggestions on the basis of the study therefore for fulfilling this third objective suggestions on the basis of the study therefore for fulfilling this third objective suggestions are given

1. There is need that the awareness and training programme should be conducted by the government for all the citizens regarding Digital India Mission
2. University should have to motivate the students for the use of different applications of the digital india.

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